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Analysis of the Effectiveness of SIWES in Enhancing Professional Development of Accounting Education Students in Rivers State Universities

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ABSTRACT

This study analyses the effectiveness of Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme in enhancing professional development of accounting education students in Rivers State Universities. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The population of the study consists of 587 accounting education students of 2024/2025 Academic Session from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, all in Rivers State. The purposive sampling techniques was adopted to draw the sample size of 155 level 200 students from the universities under study. The instrument for data collection was a self-made instrument titled “Questionnaire on the Effectiveness of Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme in Enhancing Professional Development of Accounting Education Students (QESIWESPDAS)”. The instrument was structured on a 4point rating scale, and validated by three experts, one in Measurement and Evaluation and two from Business Education Department of the Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. Test-retest method was used to ascertain the reliability coefficient of the instrument which stood at 0.77. Out of the 155 copies of the instruments administered on the respondents with the aid of two research assistants, 153 copies were successfully retrieved and used for the study. The data collected for the study was analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while t-test inferential statistics was used to test the null hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that mentorship programme of Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme enhance professional development of accounting education students in Rivers State Universities to a moderate extent, and that accounting software enhances professional development of accounting education students to a moderate extent. Based on the findings, the researchers recommended that universities and industries should collaborate to establish structured mentorship programmes that pair students with experienced accounting professionals that would provide guidance and support during students Industrial Experience Scheme, universities should also incorporate training on popular accounting softwares into students Industrial Work Experience Scheme programme to enable students develop practical skills in accounting technology.

Keywords: Analysis, Effectiveness, Students, Industrial Work Experience, Scheme, Professional Development, Accounting, Education

INTRODUCTION

Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme is structured to expose students in higher education to real-world of work environments, equipping them with hands on skills that are often missing from traditional academic curricula. The scheme serves as an essential component of Nigeria's educational strategy by fostering, a more technically skilled workforce prepared for national economic demands. Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) fosters a sense of professionalism among students (Aliyu& Musa, 2022). The insights gained during this period are invaluable, they help students to develop critical thinking complexities of the accounting profession.

The Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) experience enriches students' understanding of their future roles and employability and equips them with practical skills that complement their academic knowledge. Ogunleye (2022) stated the integration of theory and practices into Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme is crucial for the development of competent accounting professionals who can contribute effectively to their organisations and the broader economy. This is the reason why Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme is seen as a pivotal programme which is designed to provide undergraduate students in Nigeria with practical exposure to their fields of study.

Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme aims to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, thus preparing students for the realities of their professions (Ogunleye, 2022). During this period, students engage in hands on work experiences in various industries, which allow them to observe and participate in professional practices relevant to their courses. This initiative is particularly significant in fields like accounting, where practical skills and real-world experiences are essential for competence in a highly regulated and dynamic environment.

Bello and Ajayi (2023) demonstrate that students who participate in Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) show significant improvement in their ability to handle real-life accounting problems, as the programme bridges the gap between theoretical learning and practical application. This hands skills on approach enhances students professional development and readiness for the workforce. This implies that Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme is a programme of upholding standards and efficiency of human resources provided by the country's list of tertiary institutions. It is a way of harmonizing school learning with practical industrial requirements of skilled labour. According to Ojo and Samuel (2024), Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme is designed to help and consolidate school and industry collaboration of undergraduate students undergoing courses in Science, Engineering and Technology and other professional courses to acquire necessary practical skills in addition to theoretical knowledge gained in the classroom. It is a programme that uses the work environment to expose students to work methods and provide needed experience in handling tools, machinery and equipment that may not be available in educational institutions.

As an industrial attachment process, Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme extends and enlarges the learning environment and resources beyond the capabilities of the school thereby enlarging the scope and quality of practical skills that students can acquire. Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme has been noted for its positive impact on student's readiness for employment, enhancing their familiarity with professional work environments. Studies indicate that students who participates in Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme tend to perform better on job roles post-graduation, as they have experience handling equipment and following industry-standard practices. This exposure is particularly beneficial in technical fields where handling machinery and specialized tools is essential (Ugwuanyi&Ezema, 2020). It provides an opportunity for students to gain real-world experience, which is essential for their professional development. It plays a vital role in equipping students with the necessary skills, to navigate the complexities of the accounting profession. Through internships, students gain exposure to various accounting practices, tools, and technologies, enabling them to become proficient in industry standards. This hands on experience is invaluable as it prepares students for the demands of the job market and helps them adapt to evolving industry trends. Moreover, Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme faces challenges such as limited placement, funding constraints, gaps in institutional support, which can affect the equality of students training experience.

The primary objectives of the Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme is to provide students with practical exposure to the accounting profession. This objective is crucial for enhancing students understanding of theoretical concepts through real-world applications. By participating in Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme, students can observe and engage in accounting process, making their education more relevant and effective (Nwosu&Akpan, 2023). Also, Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme develop students professional competencies. This includes not only technical skills related to accounting practices but also essential soft skills such as communication, teamwork, and critical thinking. By immersing students in a professional environment, Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme aims to cultivate a well- rounded skill set that will enhance their employability. Another objectives is to enhance the professional competencies of students through hands on experience (Dambo, 2018) Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme is designed to equip students with technical skills such as proficiency in accounting software and soft skills, such as teamwork, communication and problem-solving abilities. These competencies are critical for success in the accounting field, as they prepare students to navigate the complexities of real-world challenges (Adeyemi& Musa, 2022). Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme aims to promote a collaborative relationship between academic institutions and the business community. By partnership with various organisations, universities can ensure that their accounting curriculum aligns with industry need.

For critical analyses of the effectiveness of Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme in enhancing professional development of accounting students, two component of Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme, viz: mentorship programme and the use of accounting software were considered in this study. Mentorship programmes are important aspect of the Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme which significantly impact on the professional development of accounting education students in Nigerian universities. These programmes facilitate structured relationships where experienced professionals guide students through practical challenges they encounter during their industrial placements. According to Okwor, Nwankwo and Adeyemi (2022), mentorship creates an environment of learning where students can ask questions, seek advice and gain insights from industry experts, thus bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world applications.

Mentorship provide students with hands on training and exposure to industry-standard practices particularly in the use of accounting software and financial reporting techniques. Adeyemi and Okeke (2023) found that accounting students who participated in mentorship programmes during their industrial training developed a higher level of proficiency in practical accounting tasks compared to their peers without such support. Mentorship programmes help cultivate soft skills essential for professional success. Skills such as communication, teamwork, and ethical decision making are often developed through mentorship interactions. Bello and Ajayi (2023) noted, that mentors play a crucial role in modelling professional behaviour, which helps students understand workplace dynamics and the importance of ethical practices in accounting. Such skills are not only vital for individual performance but also contribute to the overall professionalism of the accounting field. Students who engage in mentorship during Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme are more likely to secure internships and job placements on graduation. The relationships built during mentorship can lead to valuable professional connections that are instrumental in the students' career advancement. Mentorship contributes to increased student confidence and motivation. The guidance and encouragement from mentors can empower students to take initiative and pursue their career goals more aggressively. This implies that students who received mentorship reported higher levels of self-efficacy and were more inclined to engage in continuous professional development activities especially in the area of the use of accounting software.

Accounting software is a type of computer programme designed to manage and automate various accounting task such as financial transaction, invoicing and reporting and (Adebayo & Chika, 2023). These software solutions are used by businesses, organisations, and individuals to streamline their financial management processes, improve accuracy and reduce errors. According to Ogwunte and Agburuga (2021), the primary benefits of accounting software is the ability to automate routine

accounting tasks such as data entry, invoicing and reconciliations. This not only saves time but also reduces the risk of errors and discrepancies. Consequently, the integration of accounting software within the Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme therefore, plays a crucial role in equipping accounting education students with essential skills and knowledge for their professional development. Modern accounting software tools, such as QuickBooks, Sage and Tally, are widely used in the industry and provide students with hands on experience in financial data management, reporting, and analysis. Familiarity with these tools significantly enhances students readiness for the workforce, enabling them to adapt quickly to professional environments upon graduation.

One of the primary advantages of using accounting software during Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme is that it allows students to practice real-world accounting tasks in a controlled learning environment. Ibrahim and Adekoya (2023), found that students who utilized accounting software during their industrial training exhibited improved accuracy in their financial reporting tasks, reflecting a higher level of competence in handling complex accounting information. Students who mastered accounting software during their Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme demonstrated a competitive advantage in the job market, as they could effectively leverage technology to streamline account processes. The integration of accounting software within the Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme is instrumental in preparing accounting education students for their professional careers. By providing practical experience in financial management, enhancing technological skills, fostering analytical thinking and promoting collaboration, accounting software equips students with the competencies needed to thrive in the accounting profession. Ikechukwu and Abah(2023) note that accounting software training during Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme exposes students to real-world applications of their theoretical knowledge, enhancing their competency and efficiency in performing complex accounting functions, thereby enhancing their professional development.

Professional development in accounting education focuses on equipping students with the technical, ethical, and interpersonal skills needed to excel in the accounting profession. It extends beyond technical proficiency, emphasizing adaptability and lifelong learning. The dynamic nature of the accounting field, influenced by technological advancements and evolving regulations, necessitated continuous skill acquisition and professional growth. Educational institutions play a pivotal role in fostering this growth by integrating experiential learning opportunities, mentoring, and ethical training into their curricula. Ogunleye and Adeyemo (2023) affirmed that during Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme industrial placements, students are exposed to the latest accounting software and tools, compliance requirements, and ethical standards governing the profession. This exposure improves their technical skills and allows them to develop critical thinking and analytical skills as they confront real-life accounting scenarios. Furthermore, the ability to engage with clients and collaborate with team members during their placements enhances their interpersonal skills, which are crucial for effective communication in any professional setting. Again, Ogunleye and Adeyemo (2023) stressed that continuous professional development is increasingly necessary for career advancement in accounting stating that employers often prioritize candidates who demonstrate a commitment to lifelong learning and self-improvement. Therefore, the skills and experiences gained from Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme prepare accounting education students for immediate employment.

Accounting education encompasses a structured programme designed to equip students with the essential knowledge and skills needed for a successful career in accounting and finance. This education is typically delivered through a combination of theoretical instruction and practical training, focusing on areas such as financial reporting, auditing, taxation, and management accounting (Trotman, et al, 2023). In Nigerian universities, the curriculum is structured to prepare students for professional certifications such as Chartered Accountants of Nigerian qualification. However, the effectiveness of accounting education is significantly enhanced when students engage in practical experiences such as those provided by the Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme programme. Theoretical knowledge alone may not adequately prepare students for the complexities of real-world accounting tasks therefore, integrating practical training is essential. From the forgoing, accounting education is a vital component of the

academic landscape, equipping students with the knowledge and skills required to navigate the complexities of the financial sector. It involves not only the teaching of accounting principles but also developing competencies in areas such as financial reporting, auditing, tax, and management accounting. Obi and Aluko (2022), posited that accounting education aims to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical applications, preparing students for professional accounting careers by emphasizing real-world skills and ethical practices.

Statement of the Problem

The effectiveness of Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) in enhancing professional development among accounting education students in Rivers State Universities remains a concern. Despite the scheme's potential to provide students with practical skills and industry experience, many students lack adequate mentorship and guidance during their Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme placement, hindering their ability to develop essential skills and competencies. Furthermore, the limited exposure to modern accounting software and technology during Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme placements restrict students' ability to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world scenarios, resulting in a significant gap between accounting education and industry requirements. This study seeks to investigate the effectiveness of Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme in enhancing professional development of accounting education students in Rivers State Universities, with focus on the indices of mentorship programmes and the use of accounting software.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to analyse the effectiveness of Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) in enhancing professional development of accounting education students in Rivers State Universities. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the extent to which mentorship as an aspect of Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme's programme enhance professional development of accounting education students in Rivers State Universities.
2. Ascertain the extent to which practical use of accounting software enhance professional development of accounting education students in Rivers State Universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. To what extent does mentorship as an aspect of Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme's programme enhance professional development of accounting education students in Rivers State Universities?
2. To what extent does practical use of accounting software enhance professional development of accounting education students in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of accounting education students in Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) on the extent to which mentorship as an aspect of Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme's programme enhance their professional development in Rivers State Universities.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of accounting education students in Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) on the extent to which practical use of accounting software enhance their professional development in Rivers State Universities.

METHODS

The study adopted descriptive survey research design, and the areas of study in Rivers State. The population of the study is 587 Accounting Education students of 2024/2025 Academic session. The breakdown of the population shows that Rivers State University (RSU = 458) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE = 458).

Table 1: Population Distribution

S/N	Institutions	Accounting Education Students				Academic Session	Total
		Level 100	Level 200	Level 300	Level 400		
1.	RSU	42	27	38	22	2024/2025	129
2.	IAUE	142	128	115	73	2024/2025	458
	Total	184	155	153	95		587

Source: Department of Business Education Exams and Record, 2025 Academic Session

The purposive sampling techniques was adopted to draw the sample size of 155 level 200 students from the both universities under study. The instrument used for data collection in the study was a self-structured questionnaire developed by the researchers, titled Questionnaire on the Effectiveness of SIWES in Enhancing Professional Development of Accounting Education Students (QESIWESEPDAS). The questionnaire was structured on a four points rating scale of High Extent (HE – 4points), Moderate Extent (ME- 3points), Low Extent (LE-2points) and Very Low Extent (VLE-1point). The instrument was validated by three experts, two from Business Education Department and one from Measurement and Evaluation, all from the Faculty of Education, Rivers State University. The test-rest method was used to ascertain the reliability of instrument which stood at 0.77. 155 copies of the instruments were administered to the respondents with the help of two trained research assistants, out of which 153 copies were successfully retrieved and used for the study. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to test research questions, while t-test was used to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Decisions on the research questions were based on the grand mean in relations to the real limits of numbers. Therefore, items with mean with mean ratings of 1.50-1.49 were rated Very Low Extent, items with mean ratings of 1.50-2.49 were rated Low Extent, items with mean ratings of 2.30-4.00 were rated High Extent. For hypotheses, if the calculated t-value is equal or greater than the critical t-value, it will be rejected. If otherwise, it will be accepted.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does mentorship as an aspect of Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme’s programme enhance professional development of accounting education students in Rivers State Universities?*

Table 2: Mean Responses on Mentorship Programme for Enhancing Professional Development of Accounting Education Students in Rivers State Universities

S/N.	Mentorship Programme	RSU Students (n = 27)			IAUE Students (n = 126)			Aggregate Mean
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	Rmk	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	Rmk	
1.	Mentorship provides hands-on experience and practical skills in accounting.	3.08	0.53	ME	3.38	0.49	ME	3.23
2.	Mentorship provides for mentors to share industry knowledge, trends, and best practices with students.	2.91	0.58	ME	2.23	0.42	ME	2.57
3.	Mentorship programme offer guidance career paths, job opportunities and professional development.	2.94	0.59	ME	2.95	0.55	ME	2.95
4.	Mentors introduce students to industry contacts and professional through mentorship programme.	3.09	0.62	ME	3.28	0.45	ME	3.19
5.	Mentorship programme boost students confidence in their abilities and decision making.	3.31	0.49	ME	3.38	0.49	ME	3.35
Grand Mean (\bar{X}) & SD		3.07	0.56	ME	3.04	0.48	ME	3.05

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 2 analysis shows that all the items were affirmed by the respondents to a moderate extent. The standard deviation range from 0.49 to 0.59 which suggest that respondents were close to one another in their mean responses. The grand mean was 3.05, which indicates that in the respondents opinions, mentorship programme enhance professional development of accounting education students in Rivers State Universities to a moderate extent.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does practical use of accounting software enhance professional development of accounting education students in Rivers State Universities?*

Table 3: Mean Responses on Practical Use of Accounting Software for Enhancing Professional Development of Accounting Education Students in Rivers State Universities

S/N.	Practical use of Accounting Software	RSU Students (n = 27)			IAUE Students (n = 126)			Aggregate Mean
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	Rmk	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	Rmk	
6.	Practical use of accounting software enables students develop hand-on-skills in using popular accounting software.	2.82	1.09	ME	3.75	0.54	ME	3.29
7.	Students understand financial work flows transactions and reporting through practical use of accounting software.	2.75	1.10	ME	3.38	0.90	ME	3.07
8.	Students gain experience with software used in the industry through practical use of accounting software.	3.08	0.63	ME	3.15	0.36	ME	3.12
9.	Students learn to manage financial data, generate reports, and analyse result through practical use of accounting software.	3.31	0.49	ME	3.38	0.49	ME	3.35
10.	Practical use of accounting software enable students to become adaptable to new software and technologies.	3.09	0.62	ME	3.28	0.45	ME	3.19
Grand Mean (\bar{X}) & SD		3.01	0.79	ME	3.39	0.55	ME	3.05

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 3 shows that all the items were rated to a moderate extent. The standard deviation ranges from 0.49 to 0.82 which suggests that respondents were closed to one another in their mean responses. The grand mean was 3.20, which indicates that the respondents opinion, practical use of Accounting Software enhances professional development of Accounting Education students in Rivers State Universities to a moderate extent.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of accounting education students in Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) on the extent to which mentorship as an aspect of Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme's programme enhance their professional development in Rivers State Universities.

Table 4:t-test of the Difference between the Mean Responses of Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) Students on Mentorship Programme for Enhancing Professional Development of Accounting Students in Rivers State Universities

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal	Df	P-value	Decision
IAUE	126	3.07	0.57				
				0.677	151	0.290	Rejected
RSU	27	3.04	0.48				

Source: Field Survey (2025)

From Table 4 above, the t-calculated of 0.677 is greater than p-value of 0.290 at 151 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean scores of accounting education students in Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) on the extent to which mentorship as an aspect of Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme’s programme enhance their professional development.

Hypothesis 2:There is no significant difference in the mean scores of accounting education students in Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) on the extent to which practical use of accounting software enhance their professional development in Rivers State Universities.

Table 5:t-test of the Difference between the Mean Responses of Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) Students on Practical Use of Accounting Software for Enhancing Professional Development of Accounting Students in Rivers State Universities

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal	Df	P-value	Decision
IAUE	126	3.01	0.79				
				-4.88	151	0.760	Rejected
RSU	27	3.39	0.55				

Source: Field Survey (2025)

From Table 5 above, the calculated t-value of -4.88 is less than the p-value of 0.760 at 151 degree of freedom. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of accounting education students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which the use of accounting software enhance their professional development.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings of research question one revealed that mentorship programme of Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) enhance professional development of accounting education students in Rivers State Universities. This finding is in agreement with the position of Ogunleye and Adeyemo (2023) who posited that the exposure of students during Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) industrial placement makes it susceptible for them to improve their technical skills and allows them to develop critical thinking and analytical skills as they confront real-life accounting scenario. Again, the finding is in agreement with the submission of the researchers that SIWES provide students with valuable practical experience, industry exposure and skills development to enhance their employability and career prospects.

The result of the null hypothesis one showed that there is a significant difference in the mean score of accounting education students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on

the extent to which mentorship as an aspect of Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) programme enhance their professional development.

Findings in research question two showed that practical use of accounting software enhances professional development of accounting education students in Rivers State Universities. This finding is an agreement with the submission of Obi and Aluko (2020), who posited that familiarity with accounting software tools significantly enhances students readiness for the workforce, enabling them to adapt quickly to professional environments upon graduation. Also, the researcher submitted that, exposing students to practical use of accounting enable the software tools during Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme, enable them to gain valuable technical skills, improved employability, and industry readiness, setting them up for success in their future careers. The result of the null hypothesis two showed that there is no significant difference in the mean score of accounting education students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which the use of accounting software enhance their professional development.

CONCLUSION

The Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) is a valuable programme that provides accounting education students in Rivers State Universities with practical experience and exposure to real-world accounting practice. The analysis reveals that Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) enhances professional development by bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. However, the effectiveness of Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) can be further improved with proper mentorship and utilization of accounting software.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Universities and industries should collaborate to establish structured mentorship programmes that pair students with experienced accounting professionals that would provide guidance and support during Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES).
2. Universities should incorporate training on popular accounting software (e.g., QuickBooks, Xero, SAP) into the Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) programme to enable students develop practical skills in accounting technology.

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